

ISSUES OF IMPROVEMENT OF AGROCLUSTER ENTERPRISES AND THEIR MANAGEMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF FRUIT AND VEGETABLE EXPORT IN UZBEKISTAN.

Takhirjan Ganievich Yokubov

Senior Lecturer Andijan

Andijan Institute agriculture and agrotechnology.

Nematullaev Bekmirzo Bozorboy ugli
student.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8022435>

Abstract: Providing the population of Uzbekistan with food products and ensuring economic growth through the export of fruits and vegetables to the world market is one of the pressing issues of our time. This article reveals the importance of the development of fruit and vegetable growing and viticulture in our country, including in the Andijan region, and the features of improving the management system in the activities of enterprises of the fruit and vegetable cluster in this area, and also emphasizes the importance of regulatory documents for the development of the industry and the importance of the ongoing with this work

Key words: economy and agricultural sector, integration, fruits and vegetables, food security, exports, investments, cluster, greenhouses, farmers, leasing, lending, financial support.

Аннотация: Обеспечение населения Узбекистана продовольственными товарами и обеспечение экономического роста за счет экспорта плодоовощной продукции на мировой рынок является одним из актуальных вопросов современности. В данной статье раскрывается значение развития плодоовощеводства и виноградарства в нашей стране, в том числе в Андижанской области, и особенности совершенствования системы управления в деятельности предприятий плодоовощного кластера в данной сфере, а также подчеркивается значение нормативно-правовых документов для развития отрасли и важность проводимой в связи с этим работы.

Ключевые слова: экономика и аграрный сектор, интеграция, плодоовощная продукция, продовольственная безопасность, экспорт, инвестиции, кластер, тепличные хозяйства, фермеры, лизинг, кредитование, финансовая поддержка

Аннотация. Ўзбекистон аҳолисини озиқ-овқат маҳсулотлари билан узлуксиз таъминлаш ва мева-сабзавот, узумчилик маҳсулотларини жаҳон бозорига экспорт қилиш орқали иқтисодий ўсишни таъминлаш бугунги куннинг долзарб масалаларидан биридир. Ушбу мақолада мамлакатимизда жумладан Андижон вилоятида мева-сабзавотчилик ва узумчиликни ривожлантиришнинг бугунги кундаги аҳамияти ва соҳада олиб борилаётган мева-сабзавотчилик кластери корхоналари фаолиятида бошқарув тизимини такомиллаштириш хусусиятлари, ҳамда соҳани ривожлантириш бўйича қабул қилинган ҳуқуқий, меъёрий ҳужжатларнинг аҳамияти ва бу борада олиб борилаётган ишларнинг аҳамияти ёритилган.

Калит сўзлар: иқтисодиёт ва аграр тармоқ, интеграция, мева-сабзавот, озиқ-овқат хавфсизлиги, экспорт, инвестиция, кластер, иссиқхона хўжаликлари, фермер, лизинг, кредитлаш, молиявий кўллаб -қувватлаш.

The direction that gives the closest and fastest result to the lifestyle of our people in the constant increase in the well-being of the population in Uzbekistan is the organization of high-income intensive production in agriculture. Taking into account the need to fully exploit our existing potential in this, to obtain a large income for it, in recent years this sphere has been reformed with high intensity in our country.

The President of Uzbekistan, the Republic of Uzbekistan and the government engaged in the development of the economy, where fruits and vegetables that ensure sustainable development are presented, were recognized as high-quality and valid. Because fruit and vegetable growers are intensive technological products based on market research. Because the fruit and vegetable market is a \$205 billion trade product formed by etgan bir paytda, businessman ulushimiz bir percent as etmayapti. Shu called bahaga chorizia novation experience of joria etish, non-traditional exportbop fruit-vegetables products etexport efforts orcali fruit-vegetables export 2023 yilga as much as 5 billion US dollars.

The point of view of President G.M. Mirziyoyev saddorshilik lavina and Issykkhaun khukhaliklarov bashkarov enriched tizimin his aishsh, the state supplemented the proclamation of the mechanisms of Etish hydrometeorism, Yohlish agricultural cooperatives, modern tejamkor yukabatlar technologies, the quality of products and products during the meeting of the development of competitiveness of cooperation between Tajikistan and China.

These include PF-5853 of March 29, 2018 and PQ-5388 of October 23, 2019 and PQ-3978 of October 17, 2018 of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on approval of the strategy for agricultural development for 2020-2030, and PF-5853 of October 17, 2018. and the March 14, 2019 issue of "the village in the field of fruit and vegetable PQ-4239 decisions on measures for the development of agricultural cooperation can be cited.

During the meeting, the sides expressed satisfaction with the development of cooperation between Tajikistan and China, as well as the development of cooperation between Tajikistan and China.

The composition of the export of fruits and vegetables in Uzbekistan. (mln.US dollar).

Specification	2018 й	2019 й	2020 й	2021 й	2018 й.га relatively 2021йил%
Fruits and berries	357,7	406,8	353,9	280,6	78,4
Vegetables	307,7	471,3	400,0	422,0	137,1
Grape	179,7	223,7	188,3	208,5	116,0
peanut	22,9	14,4	16,5	23,5	102,6
Fresh melons and watermelons	6,5	13,1	35,6	22,7	349,2

Total:	874,5	1129,3	994,3	957,3	109,4

Thus, 2021 amounted to 1.5 million tons, or 957.3 million dollars, Teng Bulgan accounted for 60 international exports of 65 countries, as well as a fruit and vegetable complex.

While in our republic during the 9th month of 2021, 1067.1 thousand tons of fruit vegetable products were exported in the amount of 624.9 million US dollars , in the same period of 2022, exports of products in the amount of 1235.8 thousand tons or 760.2 million US dollars were achieved, which increased by +15.8 percent, +21.7 percent, respectively, compared to the same period last year.

In this, as the main import countries, Russia was able to send 379.9 thousand tons of us \$ 337.2 million, Kazakhstan 517.4 thousand tons of us \$ 159.4 million, China 61.0 thousand tons, US \$ 51.9 million, Pakistan 20.7 thousand tons of US \$ 48.7 million. Fruit vegetable products were also supplied to countries such as Kyrgyzstan, Turkey, Afghanistan, Belarus, Iran, Azerbaijan[11].

Initially, in order to ensure the effective development of fruit and vegetable production in Uzbekistan, to expand the production of high-quality and competitive finished products, to release it to major foreign markets, on March 29, 2018, by the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on additional measures for the rapid development of fruit and vegetable in the Republic of Uzbekistan" PF-5388

Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 4947 of February 7, 2017 "on the strategy of action for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", dated October 23, 2019 " on the development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2020 - PF-5853 decree"on approval of its strategy for the 2030s", PQ-4549 of December 11, 2019 " further development of the fruit and vegetable and viticultural network, in order to ensure the implementation of the decision"on additional measures to create a value added chain in the field" and to provide additional financial support for horticultural and greenhouse farms and fruit and vegetable clusters in the Republic, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of February 19, 2020 No. 102 "on measures to provide additional financial support for horticultural and greenhouse, the decisions of the Cabinet of ministers"on additional measures for the financial support of peasant farms and landlords", the decisions of the Cabinet of ministers"on the organization of state financial support for agricultural producers" dated March 11, 2021 No. 130 and the implementation of tasks set out in other regulatory legal acts related to the field will serve the rapid development of this.

The "new Uzbekistan development strategy for 2022-2026", approved by the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 60 of January 28, 2022, established the following:

Increase the income of farmers and farmers by at least 2 times through the intensive development of Agriculture on a scientific basis, bringing the annual growth of Agriculture to at least 5 percent.

Specialization of districts to the cultivation of a specific type of product.

Expansion of the scope of state support in agriculture and implementation of new mechanisms of insurance.

464,000 hectares of new and decommissioned land to be developed and allocated to clusters on an open competitive basis, reducing 200,000 hectares of cotton and grain fields and providing long-term rental to the population on an open competitive basis.

Export, as well as the development of fruit and vegetable production, increasing the area of intensive Gardens by 3 times and greenhouses by 2 times, increasing the export potential by another US \$ 1 billion"[3] were set.

President Of Our Country Sh. One of the initiatives put forward in Mirziyoev's speech at the Shanghai Cooperation Organization - summit. the idea was to develop agro-industrial clusters. he stressed that he is in favor of adopting a program to promote industrial cooperation among business circles of our countries. This innovative idea was quickly recognized by the world scientific community [3]. In It, President Sh. Based on the direct idea of Mirziyoev, the uniqueness, novelty of the innovative cotton textile cluster system being implemented in Uzbekistan, the strategic importance of the people in improving the quality of life and the export potential of the country have been analyzed in depth from both a scientific and theoretical and practical point of view.

The way in which our country is ranked among the most advanced countries of the world is the introduction of cluster systems in the agrarian sector, science, educational system and other areas.

According to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 752 dated September 21, 2018 "on additional measures for the cluster development of fruit and vegetable production in the Andijan region", diversification of Agriculture in the Andijan region, placement of varieties of fruit and vegetable crops suitable for the natural-climatic conditions of the regions, , in order to increase the material interest of participants in the process of growing and processing fruits and vegetables, The Limited Liability Companies "Premium Agro Gold" and "Navigul" and the farm "dream of a prosperous life" organized specialized model fruit and vegetable clusters for the cultivation, storage, processing and sale of fruit and vegetable products in the Andijan region, the following tasks were established:

-wide use of them in territorial conditions based on the study of advanced foreign experiments on the cultivation of fruits and vegetables, as well as the involvement of foreign specialists in the implementation of a cluster system in the field of fruit and vegetable growing;

- cultivation of agricultural products that fully meet the demand of the foreign market, their selection and seed production in the future and development in our country;

- high-yielding fruits and vegetables ecinlectic environmentalists, etishbarish products, roofing, ceta ishlash and sotish jaraenin long-standing Kulyab oluvchi tizimni, shuningdek modern innovation, tejaidigan Republic technology of fruits and vegetables products etish jaraeniga Jori kilish and phytosanitary rules are observed.

In this regard, in order to consistently implement the decisions of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Cabinet of Ministers, it is also achieved to ensure food security and increase export potential in our country by establishing fruit and vegetable cluster enterprises in the Andijan region.

In Andijan region, in 2019, the organization of the activities of agroclusters of fruit and vegetable production was carried out in two stages. Initially, 9,469 hectares of arable land of 22,764 hectares in the districts of springboarding, Khojaabad, Andijan, Asaka, Jalakuduk,

Oltinkol and fisherman were brought to agroclusters such as "Navigul KHK", dx "Andijan vegetables", "dream of a prosperous life", "Agro asia cluster", "Sadaf niholi". In the second phase, 2,463 hectares of 10,484 hectares of arable land were established agroclusters in the districts of Bostonia, marhamat, Ulughnor, Shahri Khan, Qurghontepa, Izboskan.

In total, 11,932 hectares of land in the Andijan region were attached to agroclusters specializing in fruit and vegetable production. The result was the primary processing of 62,900 tons of fruits and vegetables in the agrocluster system in 2020, the possibility of storing 27,200 tons of products in refrigerators. As a result of the implementation of new projects planned in 2021, the possibility of primary processing of 71,900 tons of products, storage of 33,800 tons of products in refrigerators and year-round delivery to the population was created.

409,426 million soums for the cultivation and procurement of products to agroclusters specializing in fruit and vegetable growing established in the region, 286,652 for the establishment of intensive garden and vineyards mln.so m, 42 197 for the launch of processing and storage capacities mln.so ' m Capital is required, these funds are carried out from domestic opportunities and at the expense of bank loans.[13]

In this case, the initiators of the project are provided with intensive garden and built greenhouses in accordance with the regulation of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on measures for the development of horticulture, viticulture and greenhouse economy within the framework of family entrepreneurship support programs approved by Resolution No. 52 of January 30, 2020 on the basis of leasing and credit conditions.

Indicators of fruit and vegetable and grape cultivation in Andijan region[11]

т/ р	Specification	Unit of measur ement	2017й.	2018й.	2019й.	2020й.	2021й.
1	Мева-резаворлар	ton	568 706	606 053	633 364	634 048	657 480
	- seed	ton	265 086	308 602	302 356	303 794	x
	-stone	ton	227 777	216 586	249 719	229 386	x
	- Walnut fruit	ton	18 722	28 255	28 975	41 604	x
	- subtropical	ton	55 380	50 982	46 804	54 079	x
	- berries	ton	1 345	407	1 568	1 916	x
2	Vegetable	ton	1478 128	1570 917	1596891	1 611 054	1 645 197
3	Grape	ton	78 849	71 247	77 630	76 817	80 896

As can be seen from the data of the table presented, the cultivation of fruit berries in the Andijan region in 2017-2021 increased from 568,706 tons to 657,480 tons or 115.6 percent ,vegetable cultivation from 1478,128 tons to 1645,197 tons or 111.3 percent, grape cultivation from 78,849 tons to 80,896 tons or 102.6 percent.

In general, today the decisions of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Cabinet of Ministers on the regulation of the activities of agroclusters have been

adopted, which is a regulatory legal document on the organization of certain clusters and the allocation of land to them.

An analysis of agroclusters operating in practice in this regard shows that the following systemic problems exist in the field:

- We believe that it is advisable to adopt a single regulatory legal document regulating agroclusters and establish the legal status of clusters;
- The organization of agroclusters, the criteria for their selection, as well as the need to improve the unified and transparent mechanisms of land allocation to them;
- The need to improve the system of formation of agroclusters in Uzbekistan based on foreign practice and the need to introduce a wide system of information and consulting services in the agrarian sector, the need to attract qualified and qualified specialists to strengthen the development of the industry;
- In the Agrolaster system, we believe that it is advisable to establish cooperation relations and implement free contractual relations, improve management using experience in the practice of jaxon in business.

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